

Nomenclature changes for some rice arthropods

T. Barrion, senior research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, IRRI

Seed bugs

In a recent review of the seed bug genus *Stollia* Ellenrieder, *Eusarcoris* Hahn became synonymized by *Stollia* (Hsieh et al 1977. A handbook for the determination of the Chinese Hemiptera-Heteroptera). Therefore, the correct names of the species formerly under *Eusarcoris* are *Stollia capitatus* (Distant) *Stollia guttiger* (Thunberg) *Stollia montivagus* (Distant) *Stollia parvus* (Distant) *Stollia ventralis* (Westwood)

Mole crickets

The revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets redefined the distribution of *Gryllotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois. Townsend stated that *G. africana* is confined to Africa and does not occur in Australia or Asia (Townsend, B. C. 1983. A revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets, Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.), Entomol. 46 (2): 183). *Gryllotalpa orientalis* Burmeister now replaces *G. africana* in Asia. The correct name for the Asian mole cricket is *Gryllotalpa orientalis* Burmeister.

Larval parasites

Mason (1981) reclassified the subfamily Microgastrinae that contains important parasitic genera – *Apanteles* and *Microgaster*-- and split *Apanteles* into several new genera. Thereafter, *Apanteles* became synonymized by *Cotesia*. The correct names for the stem borer parasites *A. flavipes* (Cameron) and *A. ruficrus* Haliday are now *Cotesia flavipes* Cameron and *Cotesia ruficrus* (Haliday). In the same reclassification, *Apanteles schoenobii* (Wilkinson) became the type of a new genus *Exoryza* Mason and therefore, its valid name is *Exoryza schoenobii* (Wilkinson). Similarly, *Microgaster russatus* Haliday was designated type of *Hygroplitis* Thomson. Its correct name now is *Hygroplitis russatus* (Haliday).

Pupal parasite

Joseph et al (1973) studied the oriental *Brachymeria* and reported that *Brachymeria lasus* (Walker, 1841) and *B. obscurata* (Walker, 1874) were conspecific. *B. lasus* (Walker) was published 33 years earlier than the latter and is, therefore, the correct name for both species.